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**Design and implementation of a full-stack web scripting environment
facilitating performance and memory usage optimized dynamic
user-provided code execution in a network-enabled embedded
lighting effect control application context**

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1. Introduction

1.1 Research goal

The research goal of this work is to design and implement a computer programming system that enables dynamically running code on an embedded system, similar to an interpreted language, but achieving a higher performance compared to most interpreter implementations.

The motivation for and primary scope of application of this system is lighting effect development without re-compiling and flashing a complete new firmware binary to the embedded device, allowing for rapid iterations and prototyping.

This process is structured into several steps:

1. Requirement Analysis: What is asked from this language/system? A survey is conducted in order to evaluate the needs of potential users.
2. System details are designed and implemented.
3. Comparison and verification: In order to benchmark both the correctness and performance of the implemented system, it is tested against a native C++ implementation in terms of runtime behavior.
4. Extensions and further applications: In this work, the scope of application for the proposed system shall be limited to functions necessary to facilitate effective programming of lighting effects to be displayed on an individually addressable LED system and/or screen. However, the implementation shall be done in a way that allows for future expansion and use in general purpose applications.

1.2 WLED

The proposed system is to be incorporated into the WLED project.

WLED is an open-source firmware conceived by the author of this work in 2016 with the goal of easily driving digitally addressable color LEDs supporting the ESP8266 and ESP32 microcontrollers by Espressif. It features an easy to use UI, a multitude of lighting effects and various third-party smart home integrations.

“WLED” is an acronym for WiFi Lighting Effects Driver.

1.3 Lighting effects

A lighting effect for the purpose of this work is defined as a rendering function that generates an array of color data to be output to a variable amount of individually addressable color LEDs, also called pixels.

This function is called several times per second, enabling changes to the data output to the LEDs. With a sufficiently fast refresh rate of at least approximately 13 FPS (frames per second)^[1], called frame rate in the following, this is observable as fluid motion to a human observer. WLED uses a target frame rate of 42 FPS by default. Due to the requirement for the effect function to be called this amount of times per second, and calculating a new color value for each connected LED, which can be up to 8000, the importance of high execution speed in the system to be implemented is highlighted. The product of the frame rate and amount of LED is called pixels per second (PPS).

Inputs to the effect function may include the current time (system clock), the colors currently displayed on the pixels and values user-supplied at runtime, which include colors, color palettes (pre-set assortments of up to 16 colors), and properties for e.g. adjusting the speed the effect propagates at.

Over one hundred effect functions are implemented in C++ in WLED version 0.13.0.

2. Requirement analysis

2.1 Target hardware

While it is desirable for the proposed system to be functional on multiple platforms with little porting effort, the primary hardware targets are boards based on the ESP8266 and the ESP32 system-on-chips by Espressif, since those are the platforms supported by WLED as of December 2021. Out of these two, the ESP32 is likely to be better suited due to its larger memory size, higher CPU frequency and dual-core architecture. Even though the effect function only runs on a single core, having the second core available can improve performance because no interrupts need to be used to handle the network stack, for example.

2.2 User requirement survey analysis

In order to assess the practical relevance of the proposed system, approximately 6000 members of the WLED Discord server, as well as users of the WLED forum forum.wled.me, which has 1500 registered users, were invited to participate in a Google Forms survey. It needs to be noted that most forum users are likely also registered on Discord, and that the survey was publicly accessible without being a registered member on either platform. Therefore, the size of the target group is estimated at 7000.

The survey was open for a period of 14 days from the 31st of August 2021 to the 14th of September 2021.

There were 884 total responses. All respondents provided at least partly valid responses, the dataset with the least answered items still contains 4 of the 26 total items. With this sample size, the respondent group is likely to be representative for all WLED users, or at minimum for those interested in more than the most basic of its functionality.

Unless noted otherwise, all percentage figures are rounded to the nearest integer.

The eight items in the survey are as following:

1. Approximately how many WLED devices are in active use within your household?

Integer entry

Of the 884 respondents, 812 (92%) respondents provided a response to this item.

Though not directly related to the proposed functionality, this item was deemed by the author to be suitable to gauge respondent proficiency regarding the use of WLED, due to a likely correlation between number of installed devices and experience/proficiency in using the application.

The average number of WLED devices from the responses given is **12.4**, however there are some outliers, the maximum number given is 3,000. This could be interpreted as respondents misunderstanding the question and entering the total number of controlled *LEDs* within their household, rather than the number of WLED *controllers*.

Another average is calculated, with these outliers excluded.

100 was chosen as the minimum threshold of exclusion, since it is unlikely that a household would have 100 separate lighting fixtures running the WLED firmware.

7 responses (0.9%) fall at or above this threshold, excluding them yields a new average of **4.3** devices.

The median of the uncorrected data set is 3.

As a reference for future works, this item highlights the importance of precise wordings in survey items. If the item asked for the number of “controllers”, rather than “devices”, likely a smaller number of respondents would have mis-attributed the term “device” to refer to an LED, rather than a controller.

2. Have you ever compiled WLED yourself?

Single choice: Yes, I've modified the code; Yes, but I only enabled a usermod or used a custom environment; No, I don't know what this means

58% of respondents stated that they did not compile WLED or do not know what that means, 24% did so, but only for minor build adjustments, and 18% stated that they modified the code. This item is included in the survey to gauge what share of the user base is familiar with WLED code and/or build tools, since the author assumes that this user group would use the proposed effect editor most extensively.

3. How likely would you use a dynamic effect system in WLED if it became available in the future? This means that you could program your own lighting effects without reflashing the entire software for every change, your changes are instantly visible.

5-value scale: Not at all likely (mapped to 1) → Very likely (mapped to 5)

With an average score of 4.3, a majority of respondents stated they would be likely to use the proposed system.

4. Would you rather use this system to make your own effects or for running custom effects others made? Answer in the middle if you'd do both, skip this question if you would not use custom effects

5-value scale: 1 = Make my own effects → 5 = Run effects by others

15% of respondents stated a strong (5), 23% a slight (4) preference towards using effects made by other users. 3% would almost exclusively (1), 6% predominantly (2), make their own effects. 53% stated they would do both equally (3).

From this item, it can be seen that almost 97% of respondents would use effects made by others to some extent. This is a strong indicator for a need for effect sharing, thus a public effect repository would likely be an essential feature for a public release.

Survey respondents were asked not to provide a response if they did not intend to use the feature. A dedicated checkbox for this purpose would have yielded more definitive data, however this is not supported by Google Forms, the survey software utilized. Out of the 884 total respondents, 883 provided responses to the single choice items 2 and 3, 882 to item 7. Item 4 has only 872 responses, therefore it is likely that approximately 10 respondents (1% of total survey respondents) skipped the item and can be assumed to neither make nor use custom effects.

5. What programming language/syntax would you prefer for making effects? (If you are filling out this form on a mobile device, you might need to scroll right to see further columns)

Multiple choice grid:

Columns: Javascript, AssemblyScript, C/C++/Arduino, Python, Basic, Lua, Custom language syntax, Graphical programming

Rows: Would not consider using, Would not prefer, Indifferent, Would prefer, Would strongly prefer, Haven't heard of this

Regarding this item, three respondents independently contacted the author with the same point of feedback. They expected to find the response "Haven't heard of this" at the beginning of the answer options rather than at the end. Combined with the fact that users may need to scroll to the right to access all options, this may have led users unfamiliar with a given programming language to choose "Would not consider using" rather than "Haven't heard of this".

The textual options are mapped to numeric score values in order to compare language desirability. "Would not consider" is mapped to 1, "Would not prefer" to 2, "Indifferent" to 3, "Would prefer" to 4, and "Would strongly prefer" to 5. As such, 5 is the highest, and 1 is the lowest possible score a language can attain.

The "Haven't heard of this" responses were not included in the calculation of averages. It was considered assigning a low value to this option, e.g. 1.5, as users unfamiliar with a given language would potentially be unlikely to learn or use it, however doing so without a reasonable argument for assigning a specific value would skew results.

Fig. 1: Languages sorted by average score and percentage of unknown answers

The first set of (blue) bars in Fig. 1 shows the languages available for selection, sorted by numeric average score in descending order. The average is out of all responses for that language, excluding “Haven’t heard of this”.

The average score of all languages is 2.87. The range, indicating the difference between the highest and lowest score value, is 1.9.

The second set of (red) bars indicate the percentage of responses with the “Haven’t heard of this” option for that language. Since “Haven’t heard of this” responses were excluded from the score calculation above, the diagram in Fig. 1 is useful to compare the two metrics.

The average percentage of “Haven’t heard of this” responses across all available language options is 8.3%.

It appears that there could be a correlation between a higher average score and a lower percentage of respondents unaware of the language, shown by the trendline in Fig. 1. This is an indication supporting the hypothesis above of a number of respondents choosing a low rating - either "Would not consider using" or "Would not prefer" rather than "Haven't heard of this" even though they may have no knowledge or notion of that language.

A notable outlier is the *Basic* option, with both a below average "Haven't heard of this" percentage of 5.7% and a below average score of 2.26.

It is possible that some users may have confused AssemblyScript with assembly code, a low-level platform specific language. However, it is in fact closely related with JavaScript.

6. What features would you like to see for an effect creator? (If you are filling out this form on a mobile device, you might need to scroll right to see further columns)

Multiple choice grid:

Columns: Real-time effect preview on hardware, Real-time effect preview in editor, Syntax highlighting, Custom palette tool, Local saving of effects, Repository for sharing effects, Custom effect parameters (sliders, checkboxes), Examples, Error detection and suggestions, Syncing across multiple instances, Optimized for computers, Optimized for mobile devices

Rows: Unnecessary, Of limited use, Nice to have, Important, Essential

Fig. 2. Features sorted by average scores

Similar to item 5, the textual responses are mapped to a numeric score: Unnecessary is mapped to 1, Of limited use to 2, Nice to have to 3, Important to 4, and Essential to 5.

With this item, it is notable that with 0.9, the distribution range of average scores is low in comparison to that of item 5 (1.9), the highest score is 4.1 (Examples), while the lowest is 3.2 (Optimized for mobile devices), which is visualized in Fig. 2 above.

This could indicate a problem with the wording of the item - a respondent is unlikely to choose “Unnecessary” or “Of limited use” for a feature proposal offering a tangible benefit. Asking whether and how much the user would utilize a given feature *themselves* could have potentially yielded more distinctive data rather than asking for their judgement whether said feature could be useful in general.

7. If using this feature required you to upgrade your WLED instance(s) from an ESP8266 to an ESP32, would you consider doing so?

Single choice: Yes; No; I already use only ESP32 units; I don't know what this means

54% of users responded that they would upgrade to an ESP32 if required for the proposed system to work. A further 35% already used only ESP32 units. 11% would not consider upgrading.

Therefore, it could be concluded that the feature would be available to 89% of the surveyed user base, even if only functional on an ESP32.

8. Do you have additional thoughts about or wishes for a custom effects functionality? Please do not leave general feedback about WLED or personally identifiable information.

Free-form text

247 (28%) of the respondents provided a response to this free-form field item.

These responses have been sorted with the labels:

- [F] for technical or UX feedback regarding custom effects
- [FE#] for feedback used as citation within this thesis
- [T] for overall approving comments without feedback or suggestions
- [NR] for general feedback towards the WLED project that is not especially related to custom effects, respondents were asked to leave only feedback for this feature specifically
- [N] Textual negations (“No”/“I do not”) or other unrelated comments.

Four respondents submitted personally identifiable information despite being asked not to do so. This information was redacted in the raw data table for privacy reasons. 19% left feedback not related to custom effects (“[NR]”), 18% left approval (“[T]”), and 10% stated they have nothing further to add (“[N]”).

129 respondents (52%) left valid feedback regarding custom effects (“[F]/[FE#]”). Of those, 25 respondents (19%) mentioned they would like support for audio reactive (custom) effects. This means that effects would be able to render based on the volume, tempo, or frequency of a sound signal supplied to the ESP via, for example, a built-in microphone, a line-in auxiliary port, or Bluetooth.

18 respondents (14%) mentioned that they would wish for custom effects to support matrices. In LED lighting, a matrix is usually a rectangular, regular two-dimensional arrangement of pixels.

Both audio reactivity and matrix support is already available in a fork^[2] of the WLED project, so it is within the scope of this work to ensure that the proposed system is expandable to support both these use-cases in the future, to be implemented either by the maintainers of the sound reactive fork, or, if applicable, once features of the fork are merged back into the core upstream WLED repository.

2.3 Functional requirements

In addition to the user requirements for the proposed system, there is also a set of functional requirements specified by the author.

There are three major core requirements:

First, the system shall allow users to implement lighting effect rendering functions as easily as possible using a client device, most likely a computer, but possibly a smartphone or tablet.

Second, changes should be previewable on the target hardware quickly without requiring a reflash/reboot cycle. This shall decrease iteration time from about 60 seconds to less than two seconds.

Lastly, the runtime performance of the function should be as close as possible to functionally identical native C++ code.

Furthermore, additional functional requirements are outlined below, which would significantly improve the overall user experience.

The system shall make it possible for the user to utilize programming structures and techniques commonly used in C++ and the majority of other languages, as long as they are likely to be relevant for effect function development. This includes numeric variables and arrays of variables, *for* and *while* loops, conditional branching (*if* statements), and functions/subroutines.

An example of a commonly used feature of most programming languages that is likely to be less relevant for effect function development is text handling. Thus, standard string manipulation functions, or even support for variable types such as *character* and *string of characters* is not a key requirement in the scope of this work.

Yet, there should be a way for users to debug the function, e.g. by printing the value of a variable to the serial terminal and/or a console within the development environment. This might necessitate some limited string support. This was also given as feedback in the user survey: “Debugging my effect is critical. Pixelblaze doesn't do a good job IMO. [...]”^[FE1] (IMO = “in my opinion”).

The scripting language used shall be intuitive for most potential users. C/C++, Python and JavaScript for example, are in widespread use and have a syntax familiar to a multitude of programmers. BASIC, COBOL or Lisp on the other hand use syntax that differs significantly from that used in most modern programming languages, and deciding upon using a syntax dissimilar from one commonly used will result in a steeper learning curve and thus less users able to effectively use the proposed scripting system.

Furthermore, the capability to develop lighting effects without physical hardware availability would be desirable, thus an on-screen effect preview inside the development environment would be ideal.

Another essential aspect is security. It needs to be ensured that the environment can solely be used to implement lighting effects. The system needs to be hardened to withstand common attack vectors. An inherent threat with scripting environments is privilege escalation.

Security issues would in the best case cause system-level denial of service, e.g. an infinite loop within user code, and in the worst case scenario allow for arbitrary code execution, e.g. a possibility to write beyond allocated buffer bounds.

To facilitate maximum cross-platform compatibility, rather than using native applications for target client operating systems like Android or Windows, using JavaScript to implement the development environment and the associated services, e.g. for uploading code to the target platform, is preferable. This allows access to the development environment within modern browsers, thus eliminating the need for platform-specific native applications.

2.4 Technical requirements analysis

The code facilitating execution of custom effects should use a very low amount of RAM (ideally less than 5 kB) without user variables. The reason is that WLED 0.13.0 on an ESP8266 only leaves about 20kB of free heap memory. Other similar ESP8266 applications utilizing wireless connectivity use a similar amount of memory, the remaining free memory is further constrained if implementing cryptographic functionality is desired.

The extra code and libraries to facilitate custom effects functionality should have a low compiled size, ideally less than 100 kB. Similar to RAM, flash size is a major constraint of some embedded systems, including the ESP series. ESP8266 and ESP32 are most commonly available with 4MB of SPI flash memory. For example, the WLED 0.13.0 binary for ESP32 is approximately 1.2MB in size. The available flash memory for firmware alone needs to be double this size, as wireless firmware updates (over-the-air, OTA) are implemented utilizing two partitions for the application code and alternating writing to them.

3. Implementation

3.1 Types of programming languages

First of all, it ought to be defined what types of languages and language evaluation systems exist. Note that all programming languages can potentially either be interpreted at the runtime of the application or compiled ahead of runtime (to machine code or an intermediate language)

Compiled languages, in case of embedded systems generally requiring a full replacement of the installed firmware. Notable examples of languages typically compiled ahead of time are C/C++.

Intermediary languages, where the source code is first translated into a platform-independent intermediate language (for example, in the case of Java, bytecode), which is then mapped to C or machine code using a platform-specific runtime environment. Notable examples include Java.

In an interpreted language, the environment directly executes the human-readable source code without the requirement of a permanent compiled intermediate. Notable examples include JavaScript and Python.

A given instruction on a given platform tends to be faster in compiled languages than in intermediary languages, which are faster than interpreted languages. It is to be noted that this is only a general observation though and actual runtime performance depends on a multitude of factors, including, but not limited to compiler optimizations, data-types, and the instruction set of the target machine, as such any observed difference in runtime can not be purely attributed to the utilized source language.

The typically superior performance of compiled language stems from the fact that the target platform merely needs to execute the machine code compiled and linked beforehand, while intermediate languages additionally need to map from the intermediate code to specific machine instructions.

Interpreted languages are associated with an even larger performance penalty, as source code needs to be parsed and translated by the target system prior to, or during execution of the program.

Since, as outlined above in the Functional Requirements section, the runtime performance of the effect function should be as close as possible to functionally identical native C++ code, this is likely to exclude all purely interpreted approaches from practical viability, though this needs to be shown empirically. Scripted code often will make heavy use of loops for iterating over ranges of LEDs, which should result in as little added overhead as possible.

Thus, the system to be designed shall utilize a language of the second type, an intermediate language. This combines the benefit of parse-/executability on a C++ engine without replacement of the firmware, one of the key design goals of the system, while still allowing for the highest possible execution speed.

3.2 Implementation structure

The project can be split into four key sub-tasks, each with some goals required for the functioning of the project and some additional goals, which are not mandatory, but would enhance the overall usefulness of the project.

First, a user interface for writing effect function code. Required functionality includes a text input area and a “Run” button or other means to compile the code and display the effect. Additionally, syntax highlighting and functionality for saving, restoring, exporting and importing code would be helpful.

Second, a parser and compiler for transforming the user effect code into the byte format executable on the target system. This should ideally be functional within the client browser, without the need for an external compilation server.

Third, networking and saving infrastructure for communication between the user interface running in the client browser and the target device.

It is required that this infrastructure supports uploading the effect byte code to the target, additional helpful features would be transmission of effect parameters (e.g. speed variable, color palette to be used) and feedback from the target, for example the frame rate at which the effect is currently running, or debugging info in case there is a runtime problem.

Fourth, an engine written in C/C++, running on the target, which can act as a virtual machine for executing the received bytecode and calling native C++ functions.

3.3 ESP32 frame rate problem

One major issue encountered during the implementation of this project was a degradation of the frame rate (which is the number of full refreshes of the displayed data per second). This only occurred on the ESP32 platform and caused a decrease of the frames per second (FPS) by a factor of 1.5-7 times. Additionally, in some cases the frame rate impact was only observable with certain lighting effect settings - for example a certain effect mode. Seemingly unrelated code changes, e.g. disabling support for an infrared receiver, using a different version of the ESP32 Arduino core framework, changing the length of an array, or running a function at a different point in the boot process all had had a profound impact on the execution speed of the effect function and/or LED driving functionality.

This led to the hypothesis that the cause could be one of the following points:

- A frequently accessed function or variable required by the effect or LED driving code is not always cached, causing expensive cache misses.
- The architecture of the ESP32 requires 32-bit aligned reads/writes. If the user code makes unaligned reads/writes, this causes the execution of further instructions, limiting performance.
- A compiler optimization with a strong impact on performance is not always incorporated. This will be tested using various compiler flags (options) of the GCC compiler. For example, a large switch structure is utilized for the selection of various different LED driver chips and methods. For performance, it would be ideal if the compiler translated this into a memory map pointing to a function for every case, rather than an *if-then-else* type of structure.

Apart from this issue hampering overall progress in the WLED project, an effective solution to this problem is essential for this thesis to deliver a significant result - it is not rational to compare different ways of implementing the same effect without ensuring that the low level LED driver code is eliminated as a potential variable. It is a basic requirement that it performs without significant differences in execution speed.

This is a difficult to debug issue since the code *is* executed correctly, just slower than expected. Furthermore, an attempt to add timekeeping to relevant functions to observe where runtimes increased failed. The reason for that is, due to e.g. the function for setting a single LED's color being called e.g. 80,000 times a second (assuming 2000 LEDs at a frame rate of 40 FPS), the timekeeping code itself had an impact on overall execution speed that was too large to draw any meaningful conclusion.

Lastly, as mentioned above, seemingly unrelated code changes can cause and/or prevent the issue. Thus, if a given code change appears to solve the issue, it is unclear whether said code is the actual root cause of the problem. The issue was reproducible by multiple users with self-compiled versions, thus eliminating the build environment and hardware instance as possible problem sources.

In order to effectively analyze the issue and compare results, a JavaScript test tool was written, which runs every effect mode for a number of seconds and logs the framerate returned by the WLED API. The recorded data can then be exported in comma-separated value (CSV) format.

The benchmarking setup was set to output data to a total of 2048 LEDs with 4 color channels each (Red, Green, Blue, and an extra White channel). Such 4-channel digitally addressable LEDs are available with the SK6812 chip. These 2048 LEDs are evenly distributed across four output pins (also called busses), thus each bus has a total of 512 LEDs. The WLED effect mode primarily used for testing is "Pacifica", which inherently runs slightly slower than most other WLED effect modes due to a large amount of trigonometric calculations.

The baseline frame rate for “Pacifica” is 35 FPS on 2048 LEDs, which means that the ESP32 can calculate a minimum of $35 \times 2048 \sim 70.000$ pixels per second (PPS). For comparison, the ESP8266 is about a quarter as fast with about 16.000 PPS.

As of the 12th of December 2021, the root cause of this frame rate issue could not yet be identified. To mitigate this issue from potentially causing variations in the observed performance of different approaches described in the following sections, the frame rate of 100 built-in effects written in C++ was measured for each compiled binary to be utilized for comparison. It was found that when using the PlatformIO espressif32 version 2.0, the impact of this issue is much lower than with the more recent 3.2.0 version, and that no seemingly unrelated code change caused a deviation of more than 2 FPS from the 36 FPS base average frame rate across all 100 measured effects.

3.4 Frame rate measurement in WLED

All FPS values given within this work are primarily obtained via the frame rate value returned by the Info page in the WLED main user interface. In case of low FPS, the result was visually verified by observing the update rate of the connected LED strip, however this is only feasible for frame rates below approximately 30 FPS, as above this value it is impossible for the author to accurately visually discern different frame rates.

```
unsigned long diff = now - lastShow;
uint16_t fpsThisFrame = 200;
if (diff > 0) fpsThisFrame = 1000 / diff;
cumulativeFps = (3 * cumulativeFps + fpsThisFrame) / 4;
lastShow = now;
```

Fig. 3: WLED frame rate calculation algorithm

Primarily for saving memory, the FPS calculation algorithm shown in Fig. 3, which is utilized by the WLED project, is cumulative. The time passed between display of the last and the current frame accounts for a fourth of the currently indicated FPS value.

The delay before that accounts for 18.75% of the current value, frames before that are exponentially weighted less.

This results in a quick, but not abrupt response of the `cumulativeFps` value to changes in the frame rate, but can lead to quickly fluctuating values at higher frame rates, as the value is averaged out over less time, for example at 200 FPS, each frame is displayed for only 5 ms, compared to 20ms at 50 FPS. To mitigate this effect in the measurements done below, six measurements were taken per test, each 10 seconds apart, and the average value used. The minimum and maximum FPS value is also indicated.

3.5 Custom benchmark effect

In order to effectively compare different embedded scripting languages and virtual machine implementations, not only based on their memory usage, but also gather an approximation of the runtime performance in a practical scenario, an example custom effect was devised. To minimize the amount of supporting functions needed, a rather trivial custom effect was chosen, which requires only four functions - getting the current timestamp in milliseconds (`getNow()`), the total count of LEDs for the effect to run on (`getLength()`), an user-settable propagation speed (`getSpeed()`) and setting a single LED to a specific RGB color (`setPixelColor(n, r, g, b)`).

```
void mode_benchmark(void){
    uint32_t t = UINT32_MAX - (getNow()/4);
    uint32_t c = 0;
    while(c < getLength()){
        uint32_t v = i%256;
        setPixelColor(c, v, v/2, 0);
        c++;
        t = (t+ getSpeed()/16 +1);
    }
}
```

Fig. 4: C++ code for the benchmark function

The benchmark effect function shown in Fig. 4 displays a moving line on the LEDs, comparable in visual appearance to a meteor. At the “tip” of this line (in the code above, for every LED c where v is a high value) the LED turns on from off to full brightness before slowly fading out to off again before repeating this cycle. This quickly moving effect makes it visually easy to identify a low frame rate.

Fig 5: Effect visualization

The resulting effect is visualized in Fig. 5 above, which depicts six still frames from the effect animation taken approximately 0.2 seconds apart from each other, from top to bottom. The frames were taken from the live effect preview in the WASM editor (see section 3.11) with a simulated LED count of 120. The visible orange gradient at the “tip” of the line is a result of anti-aliasing used in the preview. On physical LEDs, the transition would be clear-cut, one LED is on and the next one completely off. The image height is scaled by a factor of two for an improved visualization.

With 500 LEDs of the type APA102, an average frame rate of 221 FPS (minimum 192, maximum 231 FPS) could be achieved using the C++ implementation of the benchmark function shown in Fig. 4 on an ESP32. APA102 LEDs, unlike the more commonly used WS2812B, use an SPI-like protocol with both a data and dedicated clock line. This allows for them to be updated at a higher rate, thus achieving peak effect performance. 500 WS2812B LEDs have a maximum refresh rate of approximately 60 FPS (30 FPS at 1024 LEDs^[3]). In contrast, APA102 LEDs are driven at a 10 MHz clock by default, and since each LED receives 4 bytes, so 32 bits of data (8 bits each for the Red, Green, Blue, and a dimmer channel), each frame requires about $32 \text{ bits} * 500 \text{ LEDs} = 16 \text{ kilobits}$ of data to be sent. At 10 Mhz, which allows for a bus speed of 10 Mbit/s, the hardware would allow for a theoretical maximum frame rate of:

$$\frac{10 \text{ MBit/s}}{16 \text{ kBit}} = 625 \frac{1}{s}$$

, thus 625 FPS. This shows that, in this benchmarking setup, the bus speed is not the bottleneck and that the effect function speed is measured as accurately as possible.

Note that WLED normally has a maximum target frame rate of 42 FPS, this has been disabled for this and the following benchmarks.

3.6 Embedded Scripting Languages

An *Embedded Scripting Language* (ESL) is a programming language that can be embedded in and dynamically executed by an application, typically to allow customization of the behavior by a different party than the application programmer, and without the requirement of recompiling, re-linking and re-flashing the binary to make a change to the application behavior^[4]. For simple changes, a configuration file is commonly feasible, however this becomes unwieldy quickly once there is a requirement for sophisticated customized logic.

The C code executing the byte code can also be called a *Virtual Machine* (VM). The VM can be thought of as code implementing a state machine, managing program flow of, as well as memory allocation done by the embedded language.

For the given application, it is essential that it allows for a *Foreign Function Interface* (FFI), which means that the embedded language, either in the form of bytecode or interpreted code, is able to call functions from a set of predetermined functions implemented in the host language (C++).

Fig. 6: Custom function logic flow chart

Fig. 6 shows the implemented architecture by which a virtual machine for a custom effect is initialized and the custom effect function, written in the embedded language, is executed. This flow is functionally identical for both the tested interpreters - MuJS and wasm3 - which are described in detail below. WebSockets is the protocol used for receiving the custom effect code from the editor part of the system, outlined in detail below.

The exact way the foreign function interface is implemented differs with the utilized virtual machine API - the basic concept used is however identical in all three tested implementations, Elk, MuJS and wasm3. To establish an interface between the C function and its name in WASM, the VM requires three items per function.

First a string needs to be specified that defines the function name used from within the interpreted language to call the C function.

Second, a C pointer to the function to be called is required.

Lastly, the signature of the function is needed, which specifies what value type is returned by the function and the count and type of parameters it takes. This appears to be commonly given in a short string notation.

For example, `void setPixelColor(int index, int r, int g, int b)` corresponds to a signature string of `v(iiii)`, meaning no (void) return value and four integer parameters. `int getLength()` corresponds to the string `i()`, since there are no parameters and an integer is returned by the function.

3.7 Overview of available Embedded Scripting Languages

To accomplish an optimal final application within the given timeframe, it is beneficial to utilize existing resources if they fit the outlined requirements for the project.

In the given case, an *Embedded Scripting Language* (ESL) is required, since code is to be executed dynamically without changing the primary firmware binary.

In the following, some commonly used ESLs and associated projects for executing them from within a C++ application shall be discussed with a focus on their unique properties and suitability for the given project.

3.7.1 Lua

Lua is one of the most commonly used Embedded Scripting Languages. It is typically interpreted directly without an intermediate bytecode. Benefits include the wide adoption and examples available, the low resource (RAM and ROM) usage of some specialized interpreters like *eLua* (embedded Lua) and the easy binding to C code (FFI).

Drawbacks are potentially low performance in an interpreted environment - *Just-in-time compilation* (JIT) is available, but not supported on the target ESP platforms - and the unusual syntax for developers accustomed to C/Arduino, Java, JavaScript and similar languages. For example, curly braces `{ }` are replaced by keywords like `then` and `end`. Comments are denoted with two hyphens (`--`) rather than two slashes (`//`) as in the aforementioned languages.

To approximate how many developers in general are accustomed to the mostly equivalent basic language syntax used by e.g. C, C#, Java, and JavaScript, a developer survey conducted in May 2021 by Stack Overflow is analyzed. 83,052 respondents answered the question “Which programming, scripting, and markup languages have you done extensive development work in over the past year[...]?”^[5]. Of those, 65% used JavaScript, 35% Java, 34% Node.js (a framework rather than a language, but it uses JavaScript), 30% TypeScript (a JavaScript superset supporting explicit variable typing), 28% C#, 24% C++ and 21% C. The only programming language used extensively by more than 30% of respondents with a significantly different basic syntax is Python with 48%. *(all percentages are rounded to the nearest integer).*

It is to be mentioned that this is just an approximation and not conclusive evidence, since the group of Stack Overflow developer survey participants and the group of WLED users are likely to differ significantly.

3.7.2 JavaScript

Note: JavaScript is only one implementation of a language standard specified under the name ECMAScript. Since JavaScript is a commonly used and understood term, it will be used synonymously with ECMAScript in this work.

The use of JavaScript (JS) as an ESL is popular, since it is the primary language used to implement client-side behavior on websites and browser-based applications. There are a multitude of tools to execute JS (or a given subset thereof) in a low-resource C environment, these include Duktape, Espruino, MuJS, mJS, Elk and JerryScript. The tested implementations among them are discussed in detail in section 3.8.

Benefits of JS include its widespread adoption as a web programming language and its syntax, which is similar to popular languages like C and Java, as well as the ability to run it natively in web browsers, for example to implement a live preview from within a web editor.

One drawback is its implicit type system, which complicates the interfacing with C functions that have strongly typed parameters, for example `uint32_t` and `char*`.

3.7.3 DAScript

DAScript is an interesting lesser-known scripting language similar in syntax to JavaScript. It claims to feature an interpreter capable of higher performance than Lua and JS when using JIT, a property that would be of great value in the given project.

Drawbacks include low adoption so far and an interpreter ROM size that exceeds the available space on most microcontrollers without further optimization.

DAScript was not evaluated further.

3.7.4 WebAssembly

WebAssembly (WASM) is a type of byte-code that can be compiled from a variety of source languages, typically used to run code in web browsers with improved performance when compared to JavaScript. According to *webassembly.org*, “WebAssembly aims to execute at native speed by taking advantage of common hardware capabilities available on a wide range of platforms”^[6].

Any source language can be translated into WASM, if a suitable compiler is available, however using a strongly typed language as source gives the most control to developers.

Source languages include C/C++, but also AssemblyScript, which is in many relevant aspects similar to JavaScript. Compilation can be done in-browser using the AssemblyScript SDK.

The fact that WASM is a source language agnostic byte code format is a key benefit, as the compiler implementation and source language can be changed while still leaving all WASM infrastructure on the hardware target unchanged. This could even allow advanced users to utilize a traditional programming language and beginners a graphical programming framework, both compiling to valid byte code.

3.7.5 AssemblyScript

AssemblyScript is well suited as the source language for compiling to WASM, since the AssemblyScript compiler `asc` is able to run natively within the browser. No other compiler supporting WASM as the compilation target is fully functional within a client browser as of 15th September 2021 to the knowledge of the author.

AssemblyScript can be thought of as both an extension and a subset of TypeScript, which in itself is an extension of JavaScript, allowing for explicit typing of variables. In JavaScript, variables are implicitly assigned a type (e.g. `Number` or `String`), while TypeScript allows determining the type of a variable at declaration, without the possibility to reassign it to a different type.

For example, after declaring `var a : number = 42;`, attempting to assign a string value (`a = "hello";`) results in the error:

```
Type 'string' is not assignable to type 'number'
```

AssemblyScript builds upon this further, replacing the number type with dedicated types for signed and unsigned integers of various sizes (e.g. `u8` for an unsigned 8-bit integer, and `i32` for a signed 32-bit integer) and floating point numbers (`f32/f64` for 32-bit and 64-bit floats, respectively), which directly map to the associated WebAssembly types^[7].

```
export function fx() : void {
  var t : u32 = u32.MAX_VALUE - (led.now()/4);
  var c : u16 = led.len();
  for (let i : u16 = 0; i < c; i++) {
    let v=<u8>(t%256);
    led.set(i,v,v/2,0);
    t += (led.speed()/16+1);
  }
}
```

Fig. 7: Benchmark function written in AssemblyScript

In the AssemblyScript version of the benchmark function, shown in Fig. 7, it can be seen that the basic language syntax is in large parts identical to that of JavaScript and C++.

The main point likely unintuitive to a developer accustomed to C++ is, from the author's perspective, the type declaration syntax. To declare a 32-bit unsigned integer with the name *foo*, `u32 foo` would be more intuitive than the used

`var foo : u32` notation, however this design choice is understandable, since the JavaScript distinction of variables declared on a function scope with the keyword `var` and variables declared on the block scope with the keyword `let` is present in AssemblyScript as well.

Using AssemblyScript has drawbacks, it is a new language, the first release of its compiler *asc* was in 2019^[8], and tool and editor support, e.g. for appropriate syntax highlighting and error detection, is not widespread yet. As such, as also shown by the survey conducted in Section 2.2, a large quantity of users are either unaware of it or do not know how to use it yet.

3.8 Interpreter implementations

3.8.1 Elk

Elk is a very lightweight JavaScript interpreter library for C++/Arduino, requiring only about 20kB of ROM and 100 bytes of RAM^[9]. The interface is also simple and well documented. Elk was the first tested JavaScript interpreter for this reason. It implements only a subset of JS, notable omissions are `for` loops, `switch` statements, and `var` and `const` variable declarations, only `let` is supported. `let` defines a variable only in the block scope, and re-defining it is illegal. This leads to a problem, as the interpreter will retain globally set variables between executions of the JS function, thus causing an error when the variable is re-defined.

Surrounding the definition with a conditional or `try/catch` block is not possible, as doing so will scope the variable to that block and it will no longer be available outside of it.

The only way to call the same JS repeatedly identified so far is to re-initialize the runtime prior to every iteration. This has the caveat that no variables can be stored in JS variables between iterations, which is not feasible long term.

The simple sweeping benchmarking lighting effect described in section 3.5 was implemented both in native C++ as well as in JavaScript to test the performance of the system. In order to objectively assess the performance, the frames per second (FPS) value is programmatically determined after about 10 seconds of runtime.

FPS are the number of times the colors displayed by the LEDs are refreshed completely, per second. A FPS value larger than approximately 25 is required for an animation to look fluent to a human observer.

On an ESP8266 with 500 individually addressable RGB LEDs, a frame rate of 30 frames per second (FPS) was achieved with the native benchmark function. The functionally identical JS function, interpreted by Elk, achieved a frame rate of 4 FPS, almost an order of magnitude slower than the native C++ function. This result was expected, since the JS string is fully parsed and interpreted in every iteration. On ESP32, the frame rate for the same 500 LEDs and JS configuration is worse, at 2 FPS. No cause could be identified for this difference in performance, on the contrary, the ESP32 was expected to achieve a higher frame rate due to a higher CPU frequency and other architectural differences. Potentially, the frame rate issue described in section 3.3 is the cause of this result, despite all built-in effects showing no significant performance difference with the Elk interpreter compiled in, yielding 35.7 FPS on average, and 36.0 FPS without Elk.

Elk is also not ideally suitable as a final interpreter candidate for legal reasons, as its GPLv2 license forbids inclusion in more permissively licensed code, which applies to the WLED project, without relicensing the combined work to GPLv2 as well. On the 21st of October 2021, the license of Elk was changed to AGPLv3^[10], which has no bearing on its usability within permissively licensed projects however.

3.8.2 mJS

mJS, written by the same individual as Elk, is claimed to also be lightweight, albeit to a lesser extent, and features byte code to improve runtime performance. In testing, it was not possible to compile the mJS project, as it was depending on assembly code unrecognized by the PlatformIO compiler for the ESP target platforms.

3.8.3 MuJS

MuJS is the second tested interpreter, and the first engine with a byte code approach that was successfully compiled. Unfortunately, the resource requirements of MuJS are relatively heavy. Even though it was possible to compile for ESP8266, upon attempting to execute a very basic script, the controller reboots due to an unhandled out-of-memory situation. On ESP32, the script was executed successfully. 32kB of static RAM usage were observed, and although this was lowered to ~20kB by removing some error feedback strings, successful execution on the ESP8266 was still not possible. The dynamic RAM usage of the JSON object peaked up to 90kB on the first attempt on the ESP32.

Initially, performance was subpar, only 9 FPS were measured on ESP32 even with an LED count of just 1. This result was obtained using the `js_dostring()` function offered by the MuJS API, which combines parsing with the byte code execution on every frame.

To improve performance, parsing should be done only once when the effect function is called, and subsequent updates should only execute the bytecode. This can be achieved by using two functions, `js_ploadstring()` for initialization and parsing, and `js_call()` for execution. With this optimization in place, performance improved to 11 FPS with 500 LEDs. This is a fivefold increase compared to the performance observed with the Elk interpreter (see above), and while that is still significantly slower than native code, it shows that the byte code approach has potential to improve performance significantly.

Memory usage did not improve. This is expected since the parsed JavaScript byte code needs to be stored between iterations.

3.8.4 Pixelblaze

Notably, the given project is not the first attempt of using a scripting language to dynamically program LED effects. There is already an ESP-equipped commercial circuit board called Pixelblaze running a firmware of the same name. It allows for writing LED effects in JavaScript and features a live preview. The performance is by an order of magnitude superior to that observed with the JavaScript interpreters above. The software reported 112 FPS with 500 APA102 LEDs and a functionally and visually similar effect running.

Said project is closed source, therefore even though a significant amount of the source code is available in form of the JavaScript code running the web-based control panel and effect editor, it can not legally be re-used in any way. However, analyzing the API and some of the design choices implemented could give valuable insights for implementing a system that can achieve similar performance.

Upon inspection of the public API, it becomes apparent that it is designed in a way that avoids a requirement for the execution of loops in JavaScript (although they are principally supported). For reference, WLED uses a so-called effect function.

The effect function is called on every frame - that means every time the LEDs should be refreshed completely. To individually set LEDs, one will typically iterate over each LED index and set the LED to its respective value.

In Pixelblaze, a JS function called `render(index)` is used instead. This is called for every frame and for each individual LED index. Inside the render function, just the value for that LED is calculated. Additionally, a `beforeRender()` function is made available to set global variables, which are available in the render function. This allows implementing the same functionality as in a WLED effect function, but eliminating a loop in the JavaScript code, instead running it in C code. The added expense is a drastically higher number of JS function invocations from C. This approach is expected to improve performance as long as calling the JavaScript function from C is faster than the `for-` or `while-`loop iteration overhead.

The Pixelblaze client code - written in JavaScript and running in the web browser - establishes a WebSockets connection to the ESP32. The packets sent on this socket during an update to the JS effect code, and subsequently, the client code itself, were analyzed.

The default example code was used for testing. On every change of the JS code entered in the editor, a hex string is sent to the ESP in the function `sendProgram()`. This hex string represents binary data, which is generated from an array of strings that appear to resemble instructions. Thus it becomes clear that Pixelblaze uses a byte code approach to speed up execution of the subset of JavaScript it supports.

3.9 WASM virtual machine (wasm3) implementation

wasm3 is a C implementation of a lightweight interpreter for WebAssembly.

Using wasm3 from within WLED requires mostly executing a series of functions on initial load of the custom effect mode in order to initialize the virtual machine and link the callable C functions (foreign function interface).

On each animation frame, the WASM function called `fx()` is executed via the wasm3 API function `m3_CallV`.

Compiling for the ESP32, the additional flash memory used by wasm3 is approximately 78kB. An additional static RAM usage of about 32kB was observed compared to a build without custom effect support, with about 3kB dynamically used when the custom effect mode is active.

On the ESP8266, the additional flash memory usage is similar at about 74kB, however notably only 7kB of additional static RAM usage was observed.

Regardless, while both compilation and WebSockets communication were successful on ESP8266, it was not possible to load the custom effect, returning a fatal error on the first initialization step, `m3_NewEnvironment()`, of the `wasm3` virtual machine. This behavior is likely attributable to memory exhaustion, as the free RAM decreases below 11kB even with a minimal amount of LEDs configured.

The performance achieved with the benchmark effect and 500 APA102 LEDs is 119 FPS (minimum 107, maximum 125 FPS).

3.10 Integration and custom effect system overview

Fig. 8: System overview

The implemented system consists of two core components, a web editor, running inside a common browser on the client device, and an ESP32 target device.

The browser sends the WASM binary compiled by `asc`, the AssemblyScript compiler, to the ESP32 via a WebSockets connection. WebSockets is a protocol supporting bidirectional communication over a persistent TCP connection.

3.11 Web editor implementation

As outlined in the Functional Requirements, for maximum cross-platform compatibility the effect editor is to be run within a modern browser. The proof-of-concept editor implemented as part of this work can be structured into four key sub-components; the text editor interface, AssemblyScript compiler, effect preview bar and functions responsible for sending the effect to an ESP32 unit via the WebSockets protocol.

Fig. 9: Web editor layout

The layout of the proof-of-concept web editor, shown in Fig. 9, is a vertically stacked layout inspired by both the Arduino IDE and Visual Studio Code, with the most space allocated for the effect code text editor (2). Below it is the output console (3), which displays details in case of a compilation error. In the bottom is a toolbar (4) allowing various options to be set. In the very top, a live effect preview bar (1) can optionally be displayed.

3.11.1 Text editor

For the editor interface, the *Monaco* editor was chosen. This editor already implements a multitude of features commonly found in integrated development environments (IDEs), notably line numbering, syntax checking and highlighting and completion suggestions. Monaco was originally developed for and is used as the core component of the *Visual Studio Code* IDE (VS Code). According to the StackOverflow 2021 developer survey, 71% of respondents “use[d it] regularly over the past year [and] [...] want to work with [it] over the next year”^[11]. For comparison, the next most used IDE according to the survey is *Visual Studio* (not to be confused with VS Code), being used by 33% of respondents, less than half of the VS Code user base. VS Code, combined with a powerful extension for embedded development, *PlatformIO*, is also used as the primary IDE and build tool in the WLED project.

Due to both the widespread general use of VS Code as outlined above, the author anticipates users of the web editor implemented in as part of this work to be able to familiarize themselves quicker due to the similar look and feel of the VS Code IDE and the Monaco editor as shown in Fig. 10 below.

Fig. 10: Layout comparison, left: web editor interface, right: Visual Studio Code

Some challenges were encountered while embedding Monaco into the web editor. The utilized distribution of Monaco version 0.30.1 contains 105 files in 91 folders, however a majority of them are not needed in this work, for example language syntax definitions for a variety of languages. Monaco does feature native TypeScript support, however there is no official AssemblyScript support.

This caused Monaco to mark AssemblyScript-exclusive variable types like `u8` and `u32` - 8- and 32 bit unsigned integers respectively - as errors. This was mitigated by the following JavaScript code:

```
monaco.languages.typescript.typescriptDefaults
  .setDiagnosticsOptions({
    diagnosticCodesToIgnore: [2304]
  });
```

Fig. 11: Disabling various syntax error warnings

As illustrated by Fig. 11, Monaco is highly configurable in a hierarchical way, down to the parsing rules applied to certain languages.

Due to Monaco making

3.11.2 AssemblyScript compiler

asc, the AssemblyScript compiler, is responsible for compiling the AssemblyScript code the user has entered in the Monaco editor to a WebAssembly binary.

In addition to the user effect function, the compiler requires declarations of all functions accessible to the user code, this is comparable to the concept of header files in C. The following is an instance of an AssemblyScript function declaration:

```
export declare function set(index:u16,r:u8,g:u8,b:u8): void;
```

These declarations are in the file `led.ts`, which is passed to the compiler as a second source file alongside `fx.ts` containing the main user effect code.

Upon a compilation error, diagnostics are printed to the output console.

Compilation takes less than one second for the tested benchmark function on two tested Windows PCs and an Android smartphone.

3.11.3 Effect preview bar

The compiled WebAssembly binary is not only sent to the target device, it is also instantiated directly in the browser using the `WebAssembly.instantiate` API.

A repeated JavaScript function running at a target interval of 16 milliseconds calls the WASM `fx()` function to render a frame of the custom effect animation. Similarly to the C FFI implemented in `wasm3` on the ESP32, a FFI is also required for the web live preview, however calling JavaScript instead of C functions. All functions can be defined in a single JS object, as shown with the two exemplary functions ``led.set`` and ``led.now`` in Fig. 12 below:

```
const importObject = {
  led: {
    set: function(i,r,g,b) {
      leds[i] = [r,g,b];
    },
    now: function() {
      return Date.now();
    }
  }
};
WebAssembly.instantiate(fx_wasm, importObject)
```

Fig. 12: WebAssembly to JavaScript FFI

The RGB color values for all emulated LEDs are stored in an array.

The live effect preview is a narrow, empty div, that has its background set to a CSS `linear-gradient` by a repeated JavaScript function up to 60 times per second.

The gradient is constructed from the array of RGB colors populated by the WebAssembly instance beforehand.

3.11.4 Auxiliary functions

The amount of extra functionality implemented in the proof-of-concept editor is minimal and shall be expanded upon for a minimum viable product, albeit all base functionality is fully functional.

Auxiliary functions present in the proof-of-concept are an event listener that can trigger an auto-compilation some seconds after the user has stopped typing or changing the effect code, and a function to send the compiled binary to the ESP via the WebSockets connection established upon the initial page load.

3.12 Blocking user code

To protect the system from infinite loops or other instances of excessive run time usage by the user WASM function, the ESP32 implementation calls the WASM effect function from a separate FreeRTOS task, with the main task waiting for up to e.g. 250ms and then killing the task running the WASM function. This ensures that any blocking WASM code does not halt the entire main loop.

However, introducing an infinite loop into the WASM function will still cause the web editor page to freeze, as there is only a single JavaScript thread.

Although not implemented yet, Web Workers may be a suitable way to ensure the editor interface is not affected by the WASM effect function not returning, as the JavaScript will run in a separate thread.

3.13 Transport security considerations

Both recent versions of Google Chrome and Mozilla Firefox disallow insecure connections from a secure context in the author's testing. This also means that JavaScript running on a page served securely via HTTPS can not establish a connection to a server that is not secured via Transport Layer Security (TLS).

Conceptually this is a good measure to ensure the integrity of secure pages. If a secure page was allowed to make non-secure requests, attackers could still both intercept user data and inject malicious data into the otherwise secure page.

However, for the given system this presents a problem since the WebSockets connection to the ESP32 is unsecured.

In the proof-of-concept, the files needed for the web editor are served locally, however for a public deployment, the web editor files would need to be served from a web server. In order to be able to establish a connection to the target ESP32, the server would need to serve the page via insecure HTTP, which opens up some attack vectors, for example man-in-the-middle JavaScript injection for malicious purposes.

This is a high risk in comparison to a single unsecured connection just between the client browser and target ESP32 device within a local - usually home - network.

It is not feasible to serve all files required by the web editor directly from the ESP32 embedded web server as done with e.g. the main WLED user interface, as the size of the AssemblyScript compiler alone is 1MB, and this would either fill the available 1MB file system completely, or if embedded into the firmware, make the binary so large (approx. 2.2MB) that an OTA software update would no longer be possible.

A possible solution is just hosting a minimal main loader part of the web editor page on the ESP32 embedded web server, and fetching all page assets, including the AssemblyScript compiler and Monaco editor, from a secure external server.

In the long term, TLS support for the embedded WebSockets server and also the (HTTP) JSON API on the ESP32 would be helpful not only in regards to this application, but also for more secure remote control of WLED by external applications and to enable the use of browser APIs only available in a secure context - for example to access the microphone to make sound reactive lighting effects.

4 Analysis and conclusion

4.1 Validation

During and after the implementation phase, it is to be verified that the implemented system meets the requirements set out in section 2.

As for the user requirements, the source language used in the implemented proof-of-concept system is AssemblyScript, ranking last in approval within the list of eight languages users were asked about. This is suboptimal, and using a different default source language shall be considered once browser-based WASM compilation tools for other languages become available. As stated above, the WASM interpreter implementation on the ESP32 should be unaffected by a possible change of source language.

Five of the twelve features respondents were asked to rate in importance are already implemented in the proof-of-concept: A real-time effect preview is both available on the hardware and in the editor, syntax highlighting is present, (to a limited extent) error detection and suggestions are provided by the Monaco editor, and the current editor interface is optimized for use on a computer. While the editor, including crucial functionality like the WASM compilation, is fully functional on a mobile device, the Monaco editor is not optimized for use on touchscreen-only devices.

Out of the yet unimplemented features, examples and documentation in general, as well as saving custom effects locally both in AssemblyScript code form in the browser, as well as in WASM binary form on the ESP32, are the most important for a publicly usable minimum viable product.

All three core functional requirements are fulfilled by the proof-of-concept implementation. There is an editor to implement custom lighting effects on a client device. Changes to the effect function are compiled, sent to, and displayed on the target hardware within less than five seconds.

Regarding the runtime performance, with the overall system outlined above and the 500 APA102 LED testing setup as described in section 3.4, the proof-of-concept WASM implementation achieves a satisfactory performance result of 119 FPS. This is about half as fast as the equivalent native C++ implementation and comparable to the performance achievable with the closed source Pixelblaze system. The two tested JavaScript interpreters are at least by a magnitude slower.

Fig. 13 below gives a good overview over the frame rates observed with the different approaches attempted during the course of this work.

Fig. 13: Comparison of frame rates achieved with different approaches.

It remains to be shown conclusively that a satisfactory performance can still be achieved with more complex custom lighting effects and a larger set of C++ functions callable from WASM via the foreign function interface.

As an initial test, all instructions inside the benchmark function were duplicated, which yields a frame rate of approximately 78 FPS.

Most essential language functionality is supported by AssemblyScript, including functions, *for* and *while* loops, and bitwise operators.

Debugging is not yet supported in the proof-of-concept implementation.

It is easily possible to develop lighting effects using the implemented web editor without access to a WLED device due to the effect preview bar rendering the WASM effect.

The goal of running the editor completely within a web browser was achieved, as both the Monaco editor and AssemblyScript compiler can run inside a browser context. This ensures a maximum degree of cross-platform compatibility.

To ensure system security, the foreign function interface must ensure that no C functions are available to WASM code in an unsafe way. This includes, for example, passing values out of range, or calling a runtime expensive function in rapid succession. A mitigation against infinite loops was implemented successfully so as to not block the main loop.

Although beyond the scope of this work, an in-depth security audit of wasm3 would be required to ensure no WebAssembly binary can be crafted to take advantage of a buffer overflow or similar flaw and allow for a remote code execution attack vector.

Lastly, the requirement for low flash use is met by the wasm3 implementation, with around 75kB compiled size it has an impact of less than 10% on total binary size.

The additional RAM usage observed ranged between 7-35kB depending on the platform and whether the custom effect is active or not. While this usage is too high for the custom effect system to function on the ESP8266 platform in the testing carried out, the system was usable without problems on the ESP32.

With further optimizations, it may be possible to get the wasm3 VM to run within WLED on an ESP8266, but it is unlikely that such a configuration would be practically usable. This is not ideal, since 65% of survey respondents indicated that they have at least one ESP8266 installation in use (see section 2.2, survey item 7). However, as 89% of respondents indicated willingness to use ESP32 units, future adoption is likely to grow and a larger share of the WLED user base would be able to use the custom effect feature once ready for public release.

4.2 Conclusion

The fact that the proof-of-concept version implemented during the course of this work uses AssemblyScript as the source language, despite ranking last in approval in the user survey carried out, is relativized by the use of WebAssembly as an intermediary format, that is stored on and executed by the ESP target hardware. This allows for the flexibility to change the source language at any point as new solutions become available, for example a graphical code block design tool that can compile to WASM, without the need to change existing effect functions in their .wasm binary forms, or requiring replacement of the high-performance wasm3 interpreter.

Additionally, AssemblyScript is a close relative to JavaScript, so developers accustomed to it could be expected to be able to effectively use AssemblyScript as well within a short time frame.

Overall, the research goal of this work, evaluating the feasibility of, designing and implementing a dynamic scripting system for use on an embedded system in the context of the WLED lighting effect application was fully met. With wasm3, a highly suitable and performant interpreter solution was identified, yielding a performance approximately half that of native C++ code in the given application. On the basis of wasm3 and the WebAssembly bytecode it can execute, a system was implemented to facilitate effect function editing from within a common web browser using the Monaco editor and the AssemblyScript language and compiler, allowing display of the effect on the actual hardware within seconds of editing the code and thus, rapid iteration. To the author's knowledge, the implemented system is the first project to combine web assembly with high-performance LED driving on an embedded system.

4.3 Future applications and outlook

Since WebAssembly is a relatively new technology, more adoption, tooling and compatible source languages are likely to emerge in the near future.

WebAssembly in general is a promising technology with many potential applications, especially in cases where high performance is required. Suitable applications include browser high-quality graphical rendering, runtime intensive algorithms, and porting any code for in-browser use that was originally written as e.g. a native C implementation.

For the given project, merely adding loading and saving of AssemblyScript and WASM code, more C++ functions callable by the user, and several other minor adjustments are required to convert the proof-of-concept implementation implemented during the course of this work into a powerful practical custom effects engine for use in the WLED project.

The overall dynamic scripting design is not restricted in applicability to the creation of LED lighting effects - with very little adaptation, mainly defining what C++ functions are accessible from WASM user code, a multitude of other use cases can be realized.

For example, with function declarations for GPIO access, many simple Arduino examples can be recreated, which could have some advantages for learners, including not having to install the Arduino IDE, not needing to wait as long for a complete firmware upload for every change, a longer hardware lifespan due to a reduced amount of flash write cycles, and the ability to emulate the hardware in-browser to continue working even without dedicated hardware.

The system would also be useful for commercial applications wishing to remain closed source that would still like to offer the user or customer the possibility of highly granular customization, which can only be achieved practically by code modification.

5 Sources and literature

[1] Rufin VanRullen, Leila Reddy and Christof Koch
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[2] <https://github.com/atuline/WLED/tree/master>

[3] <https://cdn-shop.adafruit.com/datasheets/WS2812B.pdf> (accessed on the 17th of December 2021)

[4] https://caiorss.github.io/C-Cpp-Notes/embedded_scripting_languages.html
(accessed on the 17th of December 2021)

[5] <https://insights.stackoverflow.com/survey/2021#technology-most-popular-technologies> (accessed on the 15th of November 2021)

[6] <https://webassembly.org/> (accessed on the 14th of November 2021)

[7] <https://www.assemblyscript.org/types.html> (accessed on the 13th of December 2021)

[8] <https://github.com/AssemblyScript/assemblyscript/releases/tag/v0.8.0>

[9] <https://github.com/cesanta/elm/blob/ad796555de3a53a2efe3aad10f3e0df209983094/README.md?plain=1#L22>

[10] <https://github.com/cesanta/elm/commit/12bf4e44e4a270b55708e9d9fb9689671636c6f4>

[11] <https://insights.stackoverflow.com/survey/2021#section-most-popular-technologies-in-integrated-development-environment> (accessed on the 15th of November 2021)

The sheet containing the raw survey responses is bundled with this work and can be found in the “survey_results” folder. The proof-of-concept implementation as of the 17th of December 2021 is also bundled and can be found in the “src” folder.

[FE1] Anonymous author, location in the responses sheet: Responses!AB261

Eidesstattliche Versicherung

Ich versichere hiermit, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig und nur unter Benutzung der angegebenen Literatur und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe. Wörtlich übernommene Sätze und Satzteile sind als Zitate belegt, andere Anlehnungen hinsichtlich Aussage und Umfang unter den Quellenangaben kenntlich gemacht. Die Arbeit hat in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form noch keiner Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegen und ist auch noch nicht veröffentlicht.

Hamm, den 17.12.2021

[Signature redacted]

Christian Schwinne